

Learning science during summer vacations and its effects on attitude and anxiety towards research

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Abstract

The outbreak of COVID-19 had a great impact on education with the sudden shift from traditional to online learning. As a result, the difficulties experienced by students increased, professors had to adapt the teaching method of the contents and experimental activities were all transmitted from a screen, making this a difficult task for everyone. In this context, the resumption of in-person activities is of great importance to surpass the difficulties that this pandemic crisis has brought to students learning. Motivated by this necessity, the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), proposed a program called "Summer with Science". This program aimed to develop presential activities with the participation of students, professors, and researchers in the summer of 2020, that involved innovative solutions related to the COVID-19 pandemic. i9Masks was one of the interesting projects that emerged from this initiative and it consisted of developing transparent facial masks for preventing the virus' dissemination. This project joined students of different engineering and biological sciences at any level in a Higher Education Institution to learn science. In order to understand the impact of this course on student's motivation to conduct research, in the present study, a questionnaire was used to collect the data from the students who participated in the i9Masks summer project. The same questionnaire was applied to non-participants as a control group. After the data are gathered, the results were evaluated, and it was observed that effectively this course had a great and positive impact on student's perspective on research activities. Significant differences were observed regarding the attitudes towards research between participants and non-participants.

Keywords: Attitudes Towards Research, Engineering Education, Experimental Learning, Summer Project.

1 Introduction

The global pandemic of COVID-19 forced us to stay at home for several months and this confinement had an enormous impact on society. The closure of educational institutions and the rapid transition to digital education seriously affected students' learning and motivation, and psychological problems emerged, including frustration, stress, and depression, making this an overwhelming issue (Bestiantono et al., 2020; Chaturvedi et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2020). For this reason, the implementation of measures to improve the learning experience and overpass the difficulties that this pandemic crisis has brought to students' performance, is essential. One great initiative that contributed to this was proposed by the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), through a program called "Summer with Science". This consisted of on-site activities performed by students, professors, and researchers, both in Polytechnics and Universities in the summer of 2020, that involved innovative solutions in response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

After a long confinement, students had the opportunity to carry out in-person research activities with a grant from FCT and to have a closer involvement with the ongoing COVID-19 investigation, which piqued their curiosity. Among the interesting projects that arose, the project entitled i9Masks was fascinating. This project aimed to develop transparent facial masks for preventing the virus' spreading and it allowed students of different engineering and biological sciences at any level in a Higher Education Institution to learn science in an active and practical way, a difficult task to perform. Teaching science remains complex and challenging, and it has been stated that through engagement in scientific investigation, students' learning experience and skills/competencies are honed and they open up wide perspectives and develop better team spirit (Ballesteros et al., 2020; Gunel, 2006; Lemberger et al., 2011; Moeed, 2013; Premalatha, 2019). Nevertheless, the importance of carrying out research activities during a higher education course has not been an active field of investigation

in recent decades, existing few studies addressing this topic (McAndrew et al., 2011; Nascimento et al., 2013; Pinto et al., 2014; Saliba et al., 2019). For instance in Brazil, there is an undergraduate research program that aims to stimulate and encourage dentistry students to participate in research projects (Saliba et al., 2019). According to a study conducted by Saliba and co-workers (Saliba et al., 2019), students with scientific initiation published more papers than those without this practice, proving that this plays an important role in enhancing the experience of students in the development of scientific works. In another interesting study, also about dentistry students (de Araújo et al., 2016), was verified that scientific initiation scholarships seem to encourage undergraduate students to pursue an academic post-graduation program. In another investigation (Fava-de-Moraes & Fava, 2000), it was also stated that students involved in scientific initiation develop distinguished skills and presented better results, and need less time for finishing their thesis.

In general, the previous studies showed that the involvement of undergraduate students in research activities allows them to have a better performance in conducting research activities, namely in developing scientific papers. However, these studies focused mainly on dental education programs and on the scientific production of students.

At Portugal, many engineering students are unaware of the existence of the research as a career field until they enter university. Even then, the research experience is often introduced late in course' curriculum, in many cases only during the final dissertation, which can influence the attitude, i.e., the positive or negative feeling about doing research and the anxiety, as a fear or a concern how to do the research process. Papanastasiou (Papanastasiou, 2005) developed the "Attitudes Toward Research" scale (ATR) to explore this multidimensional factor structure based on the perception that undergraduate students usually tend to see research course methods with negative attitudes, and to feel anxiety, characterized by tension, stress, fear, and difficulties in understanding research.

In this regard, the present study aims to explore the students' attitude and anxiety in conducting research and to evaluate the effect of participating into i9MASKS course, taking into consideration the ATR scale presented by Papanastasiou (2005). To this end, a questionnaire was developed and implemented with students who participated in the i9Masks summer project and also from non-participants (control group).

2 The I9MASKS

The I9MASKS project intended to use state-of-the-art technologies for the development of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) facial masks, with characteristics such as transparency, lightness; breathability; flexibility; reuse; recycling, and efficiency in protecting COVID-19. In order to help the project implementation, a non-accredited course was designed. Aimed at engineering students enrolled at any level in a Portuguese Institution of Higher Education, the i9Masks summer course was developed to take place during the summer vacation of 2020, during a 3 months period between July and October, in two campi of the University of Minho (Campus of Azurém in the city of Guimarães and Campus of Gualtar in the city of Braga) during daytime and in an intensive and face-to-face regime. The application for the course was made through an online application, and the selection of candidates was made by curriculum analysis, namely academic merit and scientific experience in the area of the course. Twenty-one internship students were selected, of which:

- 13 female students and 8 male students;
- 10 students from the University of Minho and 3 from other higher education institutions in the North of Portugal;
- 14 undergraduate students, 6 master student, and 1 PhD student;
- 6 Mechanical Engineering students, 5 Electronic Engineering students, 3 Biomedical Engineering students, 2 Materials Engineering students, 2 Industrial Engineering students and, 3 students from other engineering courses/ areas.

During the summer course, each student was accompanied and supervised by a doctoral researcher and he was involved in laboratory work in a "learn by doing" methodology. The students attended a set of workshops (?) organized according to four modules: 1) Seminars in Science of Engineering, 2) Introduction to Research in Engineering Sciences, 3) Fabrication and Tests of Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) Masks and 4) Numerical

Simulations. Given the multidisciplinary characteristics of the project, the course involved around 17 professors and researchers from 3 research centers at the University of Minho ((MEtRICs, ALGORITMI, and CMEMS) and 5 monitors.

The students worked as a team in different laboratories for a total of twelve experimental and numerical projects implemented. At the end of the summer course, all students involved participated in workshops to present and discuss the prototypes and projects developed at I9MASKS. The feedback received from those involved in I9MASKS (teachers, researchers, monitors, and students) was very positive, with everyone recognizing the unique teaching-learning experience associated with this summer course and its potential to encourage students to become actively involved in practical engineering projects.

3 Methodology

The research questions that were examined are the following:

- (1) What are the attitudes and anxiety towards research experienced by engineering students who were enrolled in the I9MASKS summer course class?
- (2) How does this summer course participation affect students' attitude and anxiety towards research?

To assess attitudes and anxiety, a self-administered questionnaire was developed considering three groups of questions. The first group included questions to characterize the respondent, such as age, gender, course, past and present research experience. The second group considered the attitude and anxiety questions towards research. Finally, in the third group, the questionnaire included opinions and behavior questions regarding the course.

After performing a pre-test, the questionnaire was considered validated and made available to respondents through Google Forms. In the follow-up, an invitation was sent by email to the participants who had completed the summer course at the University of Minho to answer the questionnaire and to invite three or four colleagues who did not participate in the summer course ("fill the questionnaire and send the link to other colleagues to answer"), thus resulting on a snowball sampling technique.

These non-participants engineering students were considered as a control group, i.e, group in an experiment that, does not receive the intervention (Saunders et al., 2009). This control group will be used as a baseline to compare with the students who participated in I9MASKS and then evaluate the effect of the course.

A total of 47 responses were received. The age group of the respondents ranged from 20 to 33 years (mean equal to 22.06 years) and the significant majority of respondents do not have published articles. Demographic variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of students (n=47)

	Subgroup	Frequency	Percentage
Type	Participant	18	38,3
	Non-participant	29	61,7
Gender	Female	29	61,7
	Male	18	38,3
Qualification Level	Undergraduate	16	34,0
	Bachelor's degree	23	48,9
	Master's degree	8	17
Number of published research papers	0	45	95,7
	1	1	2,1
	2	1	2,1

4 Results and Discussion

The paper explores results for attitudes and anxiety towards the investigation. The questions were based on the Attitudes Toward Research (ATR) scale (Papanastasiou, 2005) with 32 items on a five-point Likert scale ranging from "1" (strongly disagree) to "5" (strongly agree). The items in the ATR can be subdivided into five subscales (Table 2).

Table 2. ATR subscales

Scale	Subscale	# items
Attitudes Toward Research (ATR) scale (Papanastasiou 2005)	Research usefulness for career	9
	Research Anxiety	8 (7)
	Positive attitudes toward research	8
	Relevance to life	4
	Research difficulty	3

The analysis is made question by question in order to obtain a more detailed evaluation of the results and, thus, to explore the differences between the two groups of respondent:

- (1) the participant's group, i.e., respondents who completed the I9MASKS summer course and,
- (2) the control group with non-participants of I9MASKS

After assessing the normality of the data with Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests, it was found that the responses of the two groups do not follow a normal distribution. Thus, Mann-Whitney non-parametric tests will be used to compare the mean of the responses between the group of I9MASKS participants and the control group (non-participants).

4.1 Research usefulness for career

Table 2 shows the data obtained regarding the research usefulness for career questions. The participant group has higher mean values, which indicate a perception of superior usefulness for career (Table 3). The Mann-Whitney tests indicate that there are significant differences in students' perception of the usefulness of research between participants and non-participants in questions 7.7 – "I will employ research approaches in my profession" ($p = 0.015 < \alpha = 0.05$) and 7.8 – "The skills I have acquired in research will be helpful to me in the future" ($p = 0.013 < \alpha = 0.05$). These results indicate that I9MASKS participants consider research an important tool for their future professional activities, suggesting the existence of a positive contribution of this course on students' attitudes towards research.

Table 3. Research usefulness for career results.

Research usefulness for career statements	Mean		Mann-Whitney p value
	I9MASKS Participant	Non-Participant	
Q 7.1: Research is useful for my career	4.44	4.21	0.550
Q 7.2: Research is connected to my field of study	4.44	4.10	0.357
Q 7.3: Research should be indispensable in my professional training	4.33	3.90	0.310
Q 7.4: Research should be taught to all students	4.22	4.00	0.457
Q 7.5: Research is useful to every professional	3.83	3.72	0.820
Q 7.6: Research is very valuable	4.50	4.24	0.432
Q 7.7: I will employ research approaches in my profession	4.33	3.62	0.015
Q 7.8: The skills I have acquired in research will be helpful to me in the future	4.61	3.86	0.013
Q 7.9: Knowledge from research is as useful as writing	4.28	4.03	0.364

4.2 Research anxiety

Given the nature of the statements, the greater the degree of agreement with the statements, the greater the respondent anxiety towards research. It follows that the control group (non-participants) has higher anxiety values compared to the group that participated in the I9MASKS summer course (Table 4). The Mann-Whitney

tests indicate significant differences in items 8.1– “Research makes me nervous” ($p = 0.027 < \alpha = 0.05$), 8.3 – “Research scares me” ($p = 0.008 < \alpha = 0.01$) and 8.7 – “I feel insecure concerning the analysis of research data” ($p = 0.012 < \alpha = 0.05$). These results suggest that participation in the I9MASKS project may help to reduce students' anxiety about research activities and makes them less frightened to carry out research.

Table 4. Research anxiety results.

Research anxiety statements	Mean		Mann-Whitney <i>p</i> value
	I9MASKS Participant	Non- Participant	
Q 8.1: Research makes me nervous	2.39	3.24	0.027
Q 8.2: Research makes me anxious	2.72	3.14	0.264
Q 8.3: Research scares me	1.89	2.83	0.008
Q 8.4: Research is a complex subject	3.72	3.83	0.719
Q 8.5: Research is complicated	3.33	3.66	0.219
Q 8.6: Research is difficult	3.22	3.45	0.430
Q 8.7: I feel insecure concerning the analysis of research data	2.56	3.31	0.012

4.3 Positive attitudes towards research

The results of attitudes towards research indicate higher positive attitudes towards research for the group of I9MASKS participants when compared with the control group (I9MASKS non-participant) (Table 5). Mann-Whitney tests confirm significant differences for 6 in 8 statements:

- Q 9.1: I love research ($p = 0.073 < \alpha = 0.10$)
- Q 9.2: I enjoy research ($p = 0.008 < \alpha = 0.01$)
- Q 9.3: I like research ($p = 0.004 < \alpha = 0.01$)
- Q 9.4: I am interested in research ($p = 0.006 < \alpha = 0.01$)
- Q 9.6: Research is interesting ($p = 0.027 < \alpha = 0.05$)
- Q 9.8: I am inclined to study the details of research ($p = 0.030 < \alpha = 0.05$)

These results suggest an increase in the I9MASKS participant's attitude towards research and indicate a possible increase in enthusiasm and interest in research when compared with non-participant engineering students.

Table 5. Positive attitudes towards research results.

Positive attitudes towards research statements	Mean		Mann-Whitney <i>p</i> value
	I9MASKS Participant	Non- Participant	
Q 9.1: I love research	3.61	3.00	0.073
Q 9.2: I enjoy research	4.11	3.21	0.008
Q 9.3: I like research	4.11	3.21	0.004
Q 9.4: I am interested in research	4.39	3.45	0.006
Q 9.5: Research acquired knowledge is as useful as arithmetic	3.83	3.72	0.578
Q 9.6: Research is interesting	4.33	3.69	0.027
Q 9.7: Most students benefit from research	4.06	3.86	0.395
Q 9.8: I am inclined to study the details of research	3.94	3.17	0.030

4.4 Relevance of research to life

The subscale of relevance of research to life has four statements, two positive and two negative:

- For the positive statements, the greater the degree of agreement with the statements, the higher the perceived research relevance.
- For the negative statements, the lower the degree of agreement, the higher the perceived research relevance.

The group of I9MASKS participants has higher levels of perceived relevance than the control group (non-participants), except in statement 10.4 – “Research is irrelevant to my life (-)” (Table 6). Even so, the Mann-Whitney tests only confirmed the existence of significant differences in statements 10.1 – “I use research in my daily life” ($p = 0.053 < \alpha = 0.10$) and 10.2 – “Research-orientated thinking plays an important role in everyday life” ($p = 0.067 < \alpha = 0.10$).

These results are in agreement with those presented previously and suggest that the I9MASKS participants consider use research in their daily lives, unlike the non-participants.

Table 6. Relevance of research to life results.

Relevance of research to life statements	Mean		Mann-Whitney p value
	I9MASKS Participant	Non-Participant	
Q 10.1: I use research in my daily life	3.72	2.97	0.053
Q 10.2: Research-orientated thinking plays an important role in everyday life	3.94	3.24	0.067
Q 10.3: Research thinking does not apply to my personal life (-)	2.39	2.45	0.673
Q 10.4: Research is irrelevant to my life (-)	1.94	1.66	0.405

4.5 Research difficulty

The last ATR subscale, the research difficulty, has three statements, all negative. In this case, the lower the degree of agreement, the lower the perceived research difficulty. The mean responses of the participant group are lower than the control group (non-participants) except in statement 11.3 - I make many mistakes in research (-) (Table 7). Nevertheless, the Mann-Whitney test found no statistically significant differences between the two groups in the responses to the statements of perceived research difficulty. It is also interesting to notice that both groups have mean values lower than 3, which suggests that both groups do not have major problems in terms of mathematics or research.

Table 7. Research difficulty results.

Research difficulty statements	Mean		Mann-Whitney p value
	I9MASKS Participant	Non-Participant	
Q 11.1: I have trouble with arithmetic (-)	2.17	2.61	0.105
Q 11.2: I find it difficult to understand the concepts of research (-)	2.22	2.50	0.299
Q 11.3: I make many mistakes in research (-)	2.83	2.82	0.747

5 Conclusions

The i9Masks summer project was a novel and successful initiative. Students from the three study cycles had the opportunity to learn from each other by doing research activities in different engineering areas after being confined for so long. Motivated by this initiative and by the commitment shown by students, it was decided to evaluate the impact of this project from the perspective of the students towards investigation.

From the results gathered, significant differences were found in the usefulness of research for career, research anxiety, positive attitudes towards research, and relevance to life indicators, which in turn demonstrates that participants have a further optimistic perspective on research compared to non-participants. Nonetheless, the results for the research difficulty questions prove that although i9Masks improved students’ confidence and perspective about research activities, they still acknowledge it as a tough task in some technical aspects.

In general, the results presented emphasize the effect and importance of presenting engineering students to research activities. “Learning by doing” is to go beyond theoretical knowledge and enter the practical field. Although in Portugal, the summer course experiences are still taking their first steps, they have a great potential for applicability and change in the teaching of engineering research. If engineering students have the opportunity to practice the process of solving a practical problem in a laboratory or on a project, they can improve their attitudes towards the engineering research process and increase the recognition of its usefulness and relevance.

“Tell me, and I forget. Teach me, and I may remember. Involve me, and I learn.”

Benjamin Franklin

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